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Bibliometric Analysis of Turnover Intention Using VOSviewer

Naila Ufiidatul Uzkiyyah¹, Ika Nurul Qamari², Meika Kurnia Puji Rahayu³

^{1,2,3} University of Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta

Correspondence: Naila Ufiidatul Uzkiyyah. Master of Management, University of Muhammadiyah Yogyakarta.
Email: naila.uzkiyyah@gmail.com

Abstract

This study aims to determine the development map of "Turnover Intention" from 2008 - 2022. This study is based on a literature study of various scientific journals conducted by searching the Scopus database, using the keyword "Turnover Intention." To get a map of research developments, the data obtained is exported in RIS format. The exported data are then processed and analyzed using the VOS Viewer to find out the bibliometric map of "Turnover Intention." The data used in the study were 302 documents. The results of the analysis show that the trend of turnover intention is highest in 2021. The institution that contributes the most research on turnover intention is Eastern Mediterranean University. Most of the research on turnover intention is published in *Frontiers in Psychology*. The author who most consistently writes about turnover intention is Karatepe, OM, who contributes 8 themes to the same research publication.

Keywords: Self Efficacy, Turnover Intention, Work Behavior

1. Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic is an epidemic that has hit almost all countries in the world. Indonesia is one of the countries affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. Corona virus disease or what is known as Covid-19 has had a tremendous impact on all aspects. From the aspect of health, education, even the economic aspect itself. Various polemics regarding the spread of Covid-19 are present among us during this Covid-19 virus pandemic. The Covid-19 pandemic that occurred in Indonesia caused the government to implement a large-scale social restriction (PSBB) policy in various regions. This policy has resulted in community social activities such as transportation, shopping centers, entertainment and recreation areas being closed (Meilianna & Astrelina Purba, 2020). In addition, the government has also implemented a policy of Enforcement of Restrictions on Community Activities or what we often hear as PPKM, even PPKM itself starts from micro-scale-based PPKM, to emergency-scale-

based PPKM, even PPKM occurs up to Level 3 and 4. determined by the government has the aim of preventing the transmission and spread of the Covid-19 virus in Indonesia (Megadita et al., 2021).

The policies made by the government certainly have an impact on all groups, one of which is the economic sector. The impact that occurred due to the Covid-19 pandemic, such as many layoffs in various industrial sectors of the economy. In addition to layoffs in various sectors of the economy, many employees who still have relationships with various companies are looking for other jobs when bonuses and benefits from where they work cannot be reduced due to Covid-19. In addition, the intention of employees who want to find other jobs will also occur despite changes in the policies of each company.

One of the important things in an organization or company is human resources, where human resources are components that help achieve the goals of a company. So that human resource management is not an easy thing, because human resource management is what determines the performance of quality employees. The thing that needs to be done in human resource management is about employee behavior. The employee behavior discussed is about turnover intention. Turnover Intention is an employee behavior that shows he wants to leave his job in order to get a job that feels better than his previous job.

High turnover intention behavior in a company can indicate that the company is less effective, can put the company in a dangerous position, reduce the efficiency and productivity of the company, which in the end the company will lose employees who have experience and a good image in the company, so they need to recruit and train new recruits (Joarder et al., 2011). When there is a Covid-19 pandemic like this, which causes many layoffs in almost all companies, this can result in high employee turnover intention. Many employees will choose to find a new company that they think is better than the previous company.

Turnover intention What happens in an organization or company can occur as a result of individual employee factors. One of these factors is the existence of conflict in the household. Work family conflicts that occur in individuals can result in turnover intention carried out by individuals. Family and work are important things in human life because work is something that can meet one's financial needs and family can meet emotional needs. While a person's financial and emotional is a matter of happiness for each individual (Novrandy & Tanuwijaya, 2022a). When responsibilities in one work and family prevent the fulfillment of other responsibilities, work family conflict will occur (Hill et al., 2004).

With this in mind, a leader in the company must continue to review and evaluate the company's performance and what causes employees to choose turnover intention, especially in this Covid-19 pandemic situation. In this context, the focus of the research objective is to explore and map out information related to turnover intention.

2. Literature Review

Turnover which means termination of employment relations between organizations and individuals. This can happen in a number of ways. Either done voluntarily or forced to quit by the organization. According to (Meyer & Tett, 1993) defines turnover as an intentional activity to leave the organization. With the employee's turnover intention, it can be seen how the organization and the human resources in it are performing, and can reduce the cost of turnover behavior (Moynihan & Landuyt, 2008).

Based on the statements of experts, it can be concluded that turnover intention is a desire of individuals or employees to leave, move or leave the organization and their work intentionally or not to another organization with the reason to get a better job. Many researchers argue that turnover intention is a phenomenon that exists in the workplace that must be prevented as much as possible because it will result in cost overruns, starting from the costs of recruitment and selection of employees, or the costs of failures that occur during the initial period. Turnover intention can also be seen as a positive phenomenon from the employee's perspective. In addition to the reasons for having received a better job offer related to material such as salary costs and or immaterial considerations (Dam, 2003).

Social exchange theory in turnover intention can be applied. In this theory it is explained that when an organization can treat employees well, fairly, and can provide rewards for the achievements that employees have given to the organization, in the end employees will feel treated well by the organization and will give their best to realize organizational goals (Dawley et al., 2008). In addition, employees will respond well by increasing employee loyalty and strengthening commitment to the organization which will not result in turnover intention (Barkhuizen et al., 2014).

3. Research Methods

The purpose of this study is to map information from previous studies regarding turnover intention. Therefore, this study is part of the literature review. Literature review is needed to help analyze and interpret hypotheses and research concepts (Hamzah & Khusnia, 2021). Literature review is an expression that is fixated on the research process that has been carried out to collect and assess research on certain problems (Triandini et al., 2019).

In this study, journals from around the world were used to source research data, the data was organized by searching the database (<https://www.scopus.com/>). This study focuses on mapping information about the dynamics of research on turnover intention, namely from 2008 to the present. Therefore, qualitative research methods using literature study are the most appropriate research methods when selected to achieve the objectives of this study. The source of the data is obtained from the Scopus database, then the data can be stored in RIS format which will then be processed using VOSviewer software.

The Scopus database was chosen because it was determined purposively with considerations and reputations that have been internationally recognized both from universities and by research institutions (Judge, 2020). Then the reason for using VOSviewer software is because it has advantages in identifying combinations of noun phrases related to mapping and an integrated clustering approach and visualization (Marthin et al., 2021).

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Development of research publications on Turnover Intention

The development of research on turnover intention in 2008-2022 experienced ups and downs. The development of research on turnover intention with the highest Scopus index occurred in 2021, reaching 30 publications or 15%.

Table 1. Turnover Intention Research Publication Year at Scopus 2008-2022

Year	Amount	Percentage
2022	18	9%
2021	30	15%
2020	22	11%
2019	25	12%
2018	15	7%
2017	12	6%
2016	9	4%
2015	14	7%
2014	7	3%
2013	13	6%
2012	12	6%
2011	5	2%
2010	4	2%
2009	9	4%
2008	8	4%
15 years	203	100%

The growth development of research publications on turnover intention in 2008-2022 based on table 1 and figure 1 shows that there is an up and down process. The least number of publications occurred in 2010 with a percentage of 2% or the number of publications as many as 4 publications and followed in 2011 which both had the same percentage of publications of 2%, which had 5 publications. Most publications occurred in 2021 with 30 (15%). There are many publications regarding turnover intention because 2021 is still the year of the pandemic that is happening in the world. Due to the prolonged pandemic that has claimed almost the entire world, turnover intention in various organizations and even companies will occur. So, with the many levels of turnover intention, there are also many researchers who write the topic of publications about turnover intention. And below that, it can be seen that in 2019 the number of publications regarding turnover intention was 25 publications, equivalent to 12%. In 2020, the number of publications decreased slightly, there were 22 publications with a percentage of 11%.

Figure 1: Turnover Intention Research Publication Year at Scopus 2008 – 2022

4.2. The Core Journal of Turnover Intention Research at Scopus in 2008 – 2022

Based on the search results with the keywords turnover intention and work family conflict on Scopus, 203 publications were obtained. From this number, it is known that the most international turnover intention publications are published in *Frontiers In Psychology* (6 publications). Based on Figure 2, it can be seen that after *Frontiers In Psychology* there are other publications that publish research on turnover intention, namely *International Journal Of Environmental Research And Public Health* has 5 publications, and the *International Journal of Human Resource Management* has 5 publications.

Figure 2: Turnover Intention Research Journal at Scopus 2008 – 2022

4.3. Turnover Intention Publisher

Based on the results of data analysis, it shows that Eastern Mediterranean University is the institution that publishes the most research on Turnover Intention, which has a total of 8 publications. Then followed by other institutions, one of which is Portland State University with a total of 7 publications. There are two institutions that have the same number of publications, namely Pennsylvania State University, and Texas A&M University with 4 publications regarding turnover intention. The same number of publications occurred in six research institutions, with the number of publications on the theme of turnover intention being at The University of Waikato, Louisiana State University, Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, University of Minnesota Twin Cities, Michigan State University, and University of Wisconsin – Madison.

Figure 3: Turnover Intention Research Publisher at Scopus in 2008 – 2022

4.4. Researcher Productivity Research Turnover Intention

The productivity of the top 10 researchers on turnover intention in 2008 – 2022 which is indexed by Scopus shows that there is only one writer who consistently writes about turnover intention, namely Karatepe, OM, with the number of publications 8. Followed by other authors with the second largest number of publications, namely Hammer, LB with total 5 publications. Researchers with the same number of publications, namely 3 publications that raised the theme of turnover intention, namely Kossek, EE, other authors were Moen, P, another author was Rantanen, J. Meanwhile, authors who had the same number of publications regarding turnover intention contained 2 topics. the same author, namely there are 5 authors including Aboobaker, N, other authors namely Aguirre, LRD, other authors namely Ahmad, MS, Bodner, T, and Bodner TE

Figure 4: Researcher Productivity Turnover Intention

4.5. Country of Owner of Scopus Indexed Publications

The contribution of research results on turnover intentions indexed by Scopus with the highest number is the United States, then followed by China, Turkey, India, Malaysia, South Korea, Pakistan, Taiwan, Canada, United Kingdom and others. The top 10 contributors to the results of the turnover intention research can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Publishing Countries Turnover Intention Research

4.6. Turnover Intention Publication Subject

The number of publications on turnover intention research based on Scopus indexed subjects in 2008 – 2022 shows that the subject of business, management and accounting is the highest subject with 94 publications. Then followed by other research subjects as can be seen in table 6.

Table 6: Research Subjects Turnover Intention

Subject Area	Amount
Business, Management and Accounting	94
Social Sciences	66
Psychology	46
Medicine	37
Nursing	22
Economics, Econometrics and Finance	14
Engineering	10
Environmental Science	10
Computer Science	9
Arts and Humanities	6
Decision Sciences	4
Mathematics	4
Energy	3
Multidisciplinary	3
Chemical Engineering	2
Agricultural and Biological Sciences	1
Chemistry	1
Earth and Planetary Science	1
Materials Science	1

Figure 6 shows that the highest turnover intention publication subjects in 2008 – 2022 were business, management, and accounting subjects with a presentation of 28.1%, followed by social science subjects (19.8%), psychology (13.8%), and medicine (11.1%), the next subject is nursing (6.6%), economics, econometrics and finance (4.2%), the next subject is engineering (3%), environmental science (3%), computer subject science (2.7%), arts and humanities (1.8%) and other subjects not described here contributed 6%.

Figure 6: Research Subject Turnover Intention

4.7. Publication Development Map Based on Keywords

Based on the number of occurrences after cleaning the author's keywords, it can be seen that keywords are often used in research. In this mapping we can see more clearly the most network nodes so that the nodes become the largest. The biggest nodes in this mapping are Turnover Intention, Work-family conflict, and family conflict. But the focus of this research is the mapping of turnover intention. The results of the keyword development map from the Vos viewer are divided into 4 clusters. Cluster 1 is red with 17 keyword items, cluster 2 is green with 14 keyword items, cluster 3 is blue with 13 keyword items, and cluster 4 is yellow with 11 keyword items, which can be seen in Figure 7 below. this.

Turnover intention is in cluster 3 which is blue. In the mapping results, it can be seen that the turnover intention node can be connected with other keyword nodes such as being connected to cluster 1, namely mental stress, job performance, satisfaction, attitude of personal health, and so on. Furthermore, turnover intention is also connected with cluster 2 nodes, such as multicenter study, career, human experiment, leadership, controlled study, and others. In cluster 3, the blue color cluster, turnover intention is connected to the keyword node organizational commitment, family work conflict, emotional exhaustion, life satisfaction, and so on. The last cluster, which is yellow, turnover intention can be connected to young adults, workload, intention, and other keywords.

In the blue cluster, it can be seen that the keyword turnover intention is also related or related to the keyword work-family conflict where there is research which states that the more individuals or employees who have problems in their household and this is also related to work, the more the level of turnover intention that occurs in organizations and companies (Afzal et al., 2019). In addition to work-family conflict from cluster 4 which is related to turnover intention, there are other related keywords from this node, namely the keyword work engagement. According to (Novrandy & Tanuwijaya, 2022b) in his research states that there is a negative and significant effect between work engagement on turnover intention. This means that when there is an era of work engagement between individuals and employees with organizations or companies, it can reduce employee resignation behavior. On the other hand, if there is a lack of work engagement between individuals and the organization, the higher the turnover rate for employees or individuals towards the organization or company. So that it will affect the image and performance of the company.

Figure 7: Co-word Map of Publications on Turnover Intention

5. Discussion

By using bibliometric analysis, a greater understanding of the literature regarding research trends related to turnover intention can be achieved. Writing about turnover intention for 15 years from 2008 – 2022 experiences ups and downs which can increase and decrease. The highest number of publications regarding turnover intention was in 2021 where there was a development from 2008 which increased to 2021. The number of publications found was 203 documents from 2008 – 2022 and is expected to increase again until the end of 2022 due to the large number of turnovers in various organizations.

Turnover intention is a termination of employment from individuals and organizations that can be carried out either voluntarily or involuntary replacement (Yucel et al., 2021). In the picture, research on turnover intention can be connected to various other keywords, such as work-family conflict, burnout, work engagement, job performance, leadership, human experiment and many other keywords. If turnover intention is associated with work-family conflict, it can be seen from previous research that when problems occur in the family, it will result in turnover intention (Yucel et al., 2021).

When individuals have demands between family, and work simultaneously and these demands can interfere with the individual's family life, it is more likely that employees will leave the organization and look for other jobs that they think can facilitate their life in the family (Anderson et al., 2002). According to other researchers, family life can affect the balance of individuals who work and this can affect organizational performance so that turnover intention can occur (Bansal & Agarwal, 2020). This means that when an individual who is married has a conflict in the household, it can be said to experience a high level of difficulty and cannot solve it in a balanced manner which can later make the individual leave work (Wang et al., 2017); (Labrague, 2020).

6. Limitations

This article has some limitations, especially in the selection and use of databases. Therefore, although Scopus is the largest database, there are journals or publications that have not been indexed, so that these journals are not given much attention. Furthermore, the topic of this paper only focuses on turnover intention which is related to work family conflict, so other variables or other aspects are not explained in detail. Another thing, the writing of this article is not specific to the object of research or focus on which industry. So, it is more explained in general about turnover intention. Therefore, future researchers are expected to be more specific in choosing industries in research topics, for example in manufacturing, hospitality, health, and so on.

7. Conclusion

The development map of the turnover intention trend that occurs in the world from year to year can experience an unstable process. The most publications that discuss turnover intention are in 2021, where in 2021 there are still many trends or ups and downs in the resignation process of employees from organizations or companies. Turnover intention can occur due to many factors. One of the factors is work-family conflict. The more work-family conflict factors that occur in employees, the higher the turnover intention in the company.

8. Suggestion

Because this study only uses one of the largest databases, namely Scopus. So, it is hoped that for further research, it is expected to use other databases such as EBSCO, Google Scholar, Science Direct, as well as Proquest and other databases to be able to see a map of the development of research trends with the same keywords. In addition, for further research, the keyword Covid-19 is also added to be more specific in mapping, also because during the Covid-19 pandemic, many individuals have resigned from the organization.(Davies, 2020). The object of research must also be included in the selection of specific keywords, so that the results of the research can also be seen more specifically(Joanna et al., 2021).

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